

Peripheral nerve injury therapeutics, including electrical stimulation, stem cell treatments, and synthetic neural scaffolds, have shown promising preclinical and even clinical results with potential regenerative treatment

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Abstract- In the U.S., peripheral nerve injuries (PNI) harm about 22 million people. The most frequent causes and types of PNI vary by demography (civilians vs. military, geography/country). After crush injuries, functional recovery is better than after transections, and better after distal injuries than proximal ones. Despite advancements in microsurgical treatments, severe PNIs remain connected to slow recovery. This review highlights new peripheral nerve regeneration approaches (e.g. electrical stimulation, cell therapies), which may lead to a shift in PNI therapeutic paradigms in conjunction with neurotrophic agents and breakthroughs in bioscaffold engineering. It also examines how synthetic neural scaffolds can aid with peripheral nerve recovery, as well as the next generation of biomimetic neural scaffolding that can aid in tissue regeneration. Neurotrophic factor-enriched neural scaffolds, stem cell treatments, and electrical stimulation have shown promising preclinical and even clinical results. The future of peripheral nerve regeneration is bright, since a combination of the aforementioned treatments may have a synergistic impact on nerve regeneration and functional recovery in patients with PNI. Stem cell technology is improving and evolving, and it has been explored through a number of methods in preclinical research for peripheral nerve regeneration. Electrical stimulation is another interesting potential treatment for PNI that may be used to stimulate axon regeneration.

I. INTRODUCTION

Peripheral nerve injuries (PNI) impact roughly 22 million people in the United States, and it is estimated that \$150 billion is spent on treating nerve injuries each year. 2 While peripheral nerves have the ability to repair on their own after damage, recovery of function following severe PNI is very varied. 3 & 4 The most prevalent causes and kinds of PNI differ based on the demographic (civilians vs. military, as well as geography/country). PNI affects the radial, ulnar, and median nerves in the upper limbs, as well as the sciatic and peroneal nerves in the lower limbs, and can cause severe impairment and have a negative influence on the quality of life. 5-7, 2. Patient age and treatment delays might have an impact on functional recovery following PNI. 8 Furthermore, the type of damage has an impact on functional results. For example, functional recovery is better after crush injuries than after transections, and it is better after distal injuries than after proximal ones. 8

Surgeons commonly utilize the Sutherland categorization method to categorize PNIs. 9 First-degree damage occurs when the axon is physically intact but demyelinated, preventing nerve transmission and resulting in sensory and motor function loss. There is no evidence of Wallerian degeneration, and functional recovery is probable. Second-degree damage is defined by axonal damage and Wallerian degeneration, but axon regeneration and function recovery are expected. Axonal damage and Wallerian degeneration are also seen in third, fourth, and fifth-degree traumas. The endoneurium is damaged in third-degree injuries, and peripheral axon regeneration and functional recovery are restricted. Endoneurium and perineurium damage occurs in fourth-degree injuries, whereas endoneurium, perineurium, and epineurium damage occurs in fifth-degree injuries. In the event of fourth- and fifth-degree injuries, functional recovery will be impossible without surgical intervention. 10

Despite breakthroughs in microsurgical procedures, severe PNIs are still linked to a sluggish recovery and can result in long-term or permanent functional impairment. Exogenous neurotrophic factors such as nerve growth factor (NGF), brain-derived neurotrophic factor (BDNF), ciliary neurotrophic factor (CNTF), insulin-like growth factor-1 (IGF-1), and others, which are known to be endogenously released by Schwann cells

during the peripheral nerve repair process, are one promising avenue of research in this field. 3 In experimental animals, the application of neurotrophic factors has been shown to speed up the regeneration of peripheral axons. In addition to a biomimetic scaffold microenvironment, "next generation" nerve conduits under development may allow for the regulated release of impregnated neurotrophic factors to best direct the regeneration of peripheral axons to their right destination. 11

The basic science and clinical literature on the use of neurotrophic factors and synthetic neural scaffolds to stimulate peripheral nerve regeneration following damage is highlighted in this review. First, this article reviews the current standard-of-care therapies for PNI, as well as their limitations. Second, based on animal and human data, examine current knowledge of neurotrophic factors in the natural healing process following PNI, as well as their prospective therapeutic applications. Third, we look at how synthetic neural scaffolds can help with peripheral nerve healing, as well as the next generation of biomimetic neural scaffolds that can help with regeneration.

This review discusses new peripheral nerve regeneration techniques (e.g., electrical stimulation, cell treatments), which, in combination with neurotrophic factors and developments in bioscaffold engineering, may lead to a shift in PNI therapy paradigms.

II. CURRENT CARE STANDARD

2.1 The Big Picture

Primary end-to-end epineural nerve repair with tension-free realignment of nerve ends is the gold standard surgical therapy for nerve damage in circumstances of minimum gap and neural tissue loss. 12 Nerve grafts (e.g., autografts or allografts), nerve transfers, and artificial nerve conduits can be used in circumstances when nerve ends can not be bridged for initial tension-free healing. Autografts, which are non-immunogenic scaffolds that provide neurotrophic factors and Schwann cells that promote peripheral axon regeneration across the lesion site, are the gold standard therapy for nerve repair for nerve gaps of more than 3 cm. 12, 13 Autografts necessitate the removal of a healthy nerve from the patient's own body, with the sural nerve being the most common source. 12 and 13 Allografts, on the other hand, are donor tissue grafts that come from genetically unrelated sources and are frequently used to treat catastrophic or segmental nerve injuries. They have no donor-site morbidity but require temporary systemic immunosuppression, which can last up to 24 months. 12 and 13 Nerve transfers, on the other hand, entail the transfer of a healthy nerve with redundant function to a distal denervated nerve near to the target muscle and are commonly used to treat brachial plexus or proximal upper extremity injuries. 13

When primary end-to-end healing is not an option, nerve conduits, also known as nerve guiding channels, can be used to treat PNI. Nerve conduits can be biological or synthetic. Autologous arteries, veins, muscles, and other bodily tissues are employed as biological nerve conduits to bridge the distance between severed nerve ends and offer protection and guidance for peripheral axons regenerating into the distal nerve stump. 12 and 14 Synthetic nerve conduits are artificial tubular structures that work similarly to natural nerve conduits, with some built to be "biomimetic," meaning they have qualities that mimic natural biological structures to aid in healing. 15 While synthetic nerve conduits have benefits over autografts and nerve transfers (e.g., no donor-site morbidity) and allografts (e.g., no immunogenicity), the key gap size for good outcomes has been discovered to be between 1.5 and 3 cm. 11

2.2 Constraints on cutting-edge surgical repair

Despite the wide range of surgical options for peripheral nerve restoration, there are still major barriers to supporting functional recovery following PNI. Even after surgery, regaining function takes a long time, is painful, and comes in stages. 16 In a meta-analysis of 623 median and ulnar nerve injuries, it was discovered that only 42.6 percent of patients had excellent sensory results, while 51.6 percent had good motor results. 16 and 17 The development of minimally invasive and endoscopic techniques for peripheral nerve repair has resulted in less tissue stress, smaller incisions, and less discomfort. Nevertheless, the risk of iatrogenic nerve or vascular injury is regarded to be greater. 18 Despite efforts to enhance the surgical technique's safety and efficacy, the prognosis for severe PNI remains dismal. Exogenous neurotrophic agents, better bioengineered scaffolds, electrical stimulation, and cell-based treatments have all been proposed and tried experimentally with promising results to supplement surgical healing of damaged peripheral nerves. The potential of exogenous neurotrophic factors and bioengineered scaffolds, which are frequently explored together, to meet some of the unmet needs in peripheral nerve healing, is the subject of this study.

III. THERE ARE THREE NEUROTROPHIC FACTORS.

3.1 General Information

A retrograde injury signal is conveyed to the neuronal soma when a peripheral axon is wounded, causing transcriptional modifications that prepare the proximal axon for development. 8 Meanwhile, a process known as Wallerian degeneration causes distant axons to break down. 8 and 19 Schwann cells transdifferentiate and abandon their myelinating phenotype in the distal nerve environment, upregulating growth-promoting genes such as cell adhesion molecules and neurotrophic factors. 8 and 19 These transdifferentiated Schwann cells serve as a conduit for regenerated axons to reach their intended destinations. 20 Neurotrophic factors, which are soluble polypeptides transported to the soma of damaged neurons to have a trophic and survival impact, are also secreted. 20

Exogenous neurotrophic factors are being studied to see whether they may be employed in the microenvironment of damaged peripheral nerves to speed up regeneration, target reinnervation, and functional recovery. During development and repair, neurotrophic factors, such as growth

factors, play a vital role in the survival, proliferation, migration, and differentiation of neurons. 6, 11, and 21. BDNF, NGF, glial-derived neurotrophic factor (GDNF), CNTF, neurotrophin-3 (NT-3), neurotrophin-4/5 (NT-4/5), neuregulin-1 (NRG-1), transforming growth factor beta (TGF), fibroblast growth factor-2 (FGF-2) and other neurotrophic factors have been identified to play a larger role in nerve regeneration. 6, 11 Endogenous neurotrophic factors are normally produced by neurons' target tissue and promptly degraded by proteolytic enzymes. 6 Because of their naturally short half-life, neurotrophic factors require a continual delivery approach to generate therapeutic benefits following PNI. 6 Exogenous neurotrophic factors have been proven to offer trophic support for regenerating peripheral axons as well as boost the regeneration abilities of Schwann cells when given in appropriate amounts. 6 and 22

3.2 Clinical trials

Enriching a biomimetic nerve conduit with neurotrophic factors to expedite peripheral axon regeneration would be a watershed moment in the treatment of PNI, especially for big nerve gaps. 23 and 24 However, safety issues and the possibility for negative side effects with the use of neurotrophic factors necessitate more investigation in animal models to find safe and effective treatment dosages in the setting of PNI. 23 However, several human clinical studies have demonstrated neurotrophic factors to be safe and well tolerated for therapy in peripheral nerve disorders²⁵⁻²⁸ and even for other neurological reasons, providing some insight. 29-36 Although these studies did not expressly address PNI, the possible lessons learnt suggest that neurotrophic factors may play a role in PNI.

Patients receiving subcutaneous human recombinant NGF injections at 0.1 ug/kg three times per week for 48 weeks in a randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled trial of 1019 diabetic neuropathy patients did not benefit significantly from treatment, which the authors attributed to insufficient dosages. The most prevalent adverse effects were injection site discomfort and hyperalgesia, myalgia, and peripheral edema. 25 Human recombinant NGF at 0.1 or 0.3 ug/kg administered subcutaneously to patients with HIV-associated peripheral neuropathy was found to be safe and well tolerated in a separate randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled trial of 270 patients with HIV-associated peripheral neuropathy. Both doses resulted in significant improvements in pain outcomes, with relatively mild symptoms such as frequent injection site pain and less fever. 26

NGF injections have been classified as a national medication in China since 2003. 28 A meta-analysis of 64 trials involving 6297 individuals was conducted, with the majority of the trials employing mouse NGF and intramuscular injections ranging from 4 to 30 ug. 28 These findings demonstrated that NGF boosts average conduction velocity greatly when compared to controls and backed up NGF's safety profile for usage in neurological illnesses. 28

Other clinical studies using NGF for reasons other than peripheral nerve diseases still give useful information on the safety profile of these biologics. Ex vivo NGF gene delivery (including genetic alteration of autologous fibroblast cells in vitro) was used to evaluate NGF in early stage Alzheimer's disease in eight individuals with mild Alzheimer's disease. 37 After monitoring patients for 18 to 24 months, no long-term deleterious effects were detected that could be attributed to the administration of NGF. 37 There was no cell damage or tumor growth after 7 years of post-mortem investigation. 29 All of the patients had trophic responses, such as axonal sprouting and cell hypertrophy. 29. NGF concentrations in one patient exceeded physiological values 50-fold after just one year, whereas NGF levels in another patient were 2-fold higher after seven years. 29 Another clinical experiment used an adeno-associated viral (AAV) vector (serotype 2) to deliver NGF to 49 Alzheimer's disease patients, which was shown to be safe and well tolerated after two years. 30 NGF has therefore been proved to be safe for therapeutic treatment in both the central and peripheral nervous systems on several occasions.

Other neurotrophic factors have also been studied in the nervous system and shown to be safe, especially when administered locally rather than systemically. CNTF has been studied in humans for amyotrophic lateral sclerosis (ALS), with subcutaneous injections causing toxicity (anorexia, weight loss, exhaustion, and viral-like symptoms), but not intrathecally given CNTF. 38 IGF-I, which has been found to enhance sensory and motor neuron regeneration, has also been studied in ALS. 32 IGF-I was demonstrated to be safe and well tolerated when supplied by subcutaneous injections in several ALS studies. 39, 40 BDNF has been evaluated in ALS patients at doses of 25 or 100 ug/kg per day for moderate side effects such as injection site responses, diarrhea, and bowel urgency. 41 When pumped into the putamen via minipumps or given intrathecally, GDNF has shown a satisfactory safety profile in many clinical studies for the treatment of Parkinson's disease. 35

There are no published clinical trials investigating the use of neurotrophic agents for peripheral nerve damage that we are aware of (PNI). Nonetheless, the results of several clinical trials examining neurotrophic factors in the nervous system point to a favorable safety profile for their prospective therapeutic application in PNI.

3.3 Security

While human research has revealed that NGF treatments are well tolerated and have relatively few side effects, animal research has provided crucial insights into the safety of neurotrophic factors for PNI. The concentration of neurotrophic factors used has been discovered to be an important factor in maximizing their utilization. One study found that neurotrophic factors like GDNF and BDNF can affect peripheral nerve regeneration in a dose-dependent manner. 22 In terms of safety, it has been demonstrated that too high GDNF concentrations might hinder axon regeneration by producing axonal trapping at overexpression locations, a condition known as the "candy-store effect." 42, 22 While safety

is critical in the design and implementation of future neurotrophic factor clinical trials, it is equally critical to examine the most effective techniques for delivering these factors to damaged neurons for optimum effectiveness.

3.4 Neurotrophic factor delivery

Several ways of optimizing the therapeutic distribution of neurotrophic factors to the damaged peripheral nerve have been developed and tested in animals, and are summarized in the following sections. We focused on ways that might improve the temporal and spatial regulation of neurotrophic factor administration in particular.

3.5 Delivery system containing heparin

Based on moderate to high-affinity electrostatic interactions between heparin-binding sites on neurotrophic factors and sulfated groups on heparin, heparin can immobilize neurotrophic factors when utilized as a delivery vehicle. 43 Heparin prevents neurotrophic factors from degrading quickly, allowing them to be released gradually over time. 43

In a rat sciatic nerve damage model, Lee et colleagues employed heparin-binding peptides covalently fixed inside a fibrin matrix for the regulated administration of NGF. 43 The number of axons regenerating through silicon conduits was not significantly different between isografts from syngeneic donor animals and NGF dosages of 20 or 50 ng/mL utilizing this delivery technique, according to the investigators. 43 These findings are interesting from a therapeutic standpoint because they show that synthetic nerve conduits boosted with neurotrophic factors may be able to stimulate the same level of regeneration as a nerve transplant in humans without losing a healthy nerve.

Roam et al offer ways of promoting the regulated release of GDNF in gradient distribution using heparin covalently bonded to poly (ethylene glycol) (PEG) microspheres as a delivery mechanism. 44 The role of microspheres and growth factor spatial patterning in promoting axon regeneration is described in the next sections.

3.6 Microspheres

Microspheres are microscopic biocompatible particles that may be manufactured from a variety of biomaterials (e.g., poly (lactic-co-glycolic acid) [PLGA], poly (caprolactone) [PCL], chitosan, alginate, and others) to allow the slow release of neurotrophic factors in vivo. 45-47 In a peroneal nerve damage rat model, Tajdaran et al found that GDNF administered through fibrin gel filled with PLGA microspheres twice the amount of regeneration seen in controls. 46 Furthermore, Vogelien et colleagues demonstrated that calcium alginate prolonged-release-capsules (PRC) may be utilized to constantly release BDNF in a sciatic nerve damage rat model, speeding axon regeneration (relative to untreated controls) and lowering measures of neuropathic pain. 47 Another use of microspheres in PNI animal models involves Yu et al., who discovered that using NGF-containing polymeric microspheres with cellular grafts improved peripheral nerve regeneration and muscle reinnervation, although this advantage was statistically smaller than that provided by autografts. 48

3.7 Fibrin sealants

Surgeons frequently utilize fibrin sealants, which are biocompatible and biodegradable tissue adhesives. 49 Neurotrophic factors can be released gradually in vivo using fibrin sealants enriched with them. 50 The ability of these neurotrophic factor-enriched fibrin sealants to promote peripheral nerve regeneration in rats was tested by applying them to transected sciatic nerves. 50 The use of NGF-rich fibrin sealants improved motor axon regeneration and recovery. 50 GDNF caused sensory function to recover faster, but it also exacerbated indications of neuropathic pain. 50 Despite the fact that the application of fibrin sealants containing GDNF and NGF enhanced functional recovery, substantial impairments remained until the end of the study. 50 There was no discernible improvement in motor or sensory function after using fibrin sealants with acidic FGF. 50

3.8 Magnetic nanoparticles

In vivo testing has revealed that magnetic nanoparticles do not cause inflammation or interfere with the spontaneous regeneration of peripheral nerves, suggesting a satisfactory safety profile. 51 Magnetic nanoparticles functionalized with neurotrophic factors can be utilized to protect neurotrophic factors from degradation. 51 The angiogenic factor vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF) may help peripheral nerve healing by increasing vascularization. 51 When introduced to synthetic nerve conduits, magnetic nanoparticles for spatially and temporally regulated release of NGF and VEGF improved median nerve regeneration and recovery of motor function compared to mice receiving the same neurotrophic factors without magnetic nanoparticles. 51 Magnetic nanoparticles also have the benefit of being able to be steered remotely using magnetic fields and confined to areas of nerve conduits where neurotrophic factor concentrations are inadequate to allow regeneration across the lesion site. 51

3.9 Cellular and gene treatments

In the 1990s, genetically engineered fibroblasts were employed to transport CNTF and NGF to a damaged rat spinal cord in a primate model of Huntington's disease. 52, 20 Since then, similar solutions for PNI models have been presented and evaluated. AAV and lentiviral vectors are candidate vectors for several of these suggested therapeutics. By overexpressing FGF-2 in Schwann cells and grafting them into peripheral nerve lesion sites, neurotrophic factor gene treatments have been demonstrated to drive peripheral axon regeneration and myelination. 53

Indeed, Schwann cells play a critical part in the spontaneous regeneration of peripheral nerves following damage, and such transplantation procedures may be beneficial since indigenous Schwann cells' pro-regenerative phenotype might decline over lengthy periods of denervation. 53

One work emphasizes the use of conditional lentiviral GDNF overexpression from transplanted Schwann cells and cellular nerve allografts with endoneurial tubes and extracellular matrix components that mimic an autograft to supply GDNF in a geographically and temporally regulated way. 42 Four weeks of conditional GDNF expression was insufficient to elicit regeneration across the lesion site and into the distal nerve end in a rat sciatic nerve injury model, and that 8 weeks of conditional GDNF expression also resulted in unfavorable outcomes, likely due to axonal entrapment. 42 The rats that received 6 weeks of conditional GDNF overexpression showed the most axon regeneration and muscle mass recovery. 42 As a result, the study's most important discovery is that the timing of GDNF expression is critical for maximum functional recovery.

In rat sciatic nerve injury models, overexpression of GDNF or NGF has been shown to promote peripheral axon regeneration, reduce muscle atrophy, and/or enhance nerve conduction velocity in experiments employing modified Schwann cells. 54, 55

Hoyng et al., on the other hand, believe that gene therapies for peripheral nerve injuries are still a long way off, and that more systematic studies in rodent models are needed to figure out how to best deliver genes to Schwann cells, which vectors are the safest, and the best dosing and timing of neurotrophic factors. 53

Adult tissue regeneration, at its most basic level, needs chromatin remodeling mediated by master transcription factors in order to activate the transcriptional programs that allow regeneration to take place. 56 Overexpression of a transcription factor termed c-jun in Schwann cells can boost neurotrophic factor expression, but knocking down this gene prevents axon regrowth. 53 Discovering the transcriptional regulators required to maintain the pro-regenerative phenotype that Schwann cells acquire after PNI is an exciting hypothesis. 53 Gene therapy might be utilized to transcriptionally reprogram Schwann cells before grafting to boost regeneration or to maintain a pro-regenerative phenotype in endogenous Schwann cells throughout time. To fully exploit the therapeutic potential of Schwann cells for PNI, better knowledge of fundamental Schwann cell biology and transcriptional processes that promote peripheral nerve regeneration is likely required.

Apart from genetically editing and transplanting Schwann cells, another method for delivering neurotrophic factors to wounded neurons is to use genetically modified autografts. 53 Overexpression of VEGF in autografts resulted in hypervascularization, whereas overexpression of BDNF and GDNF increased motor axon regeneration into grafts, and overexpression of NGF increased sensory axon regeneration and Schwann cell proliferation into grafts, according to Hoyng et al. 53 Their findings, however, revealed that long-term expression of neurotrophic factors in an autograft did not improve distal regeneration and instead hampered functional recovery. 53 Nonetheless, the modality-specific effects of each of these neurotrophic agents were underlined in this investigation. 53 It's worth noting that if NGF induces excessive sensory neuron regeneration, it might have side effects that harm the quality of life, such as hypersensitivity, 53, as shown in prior NGF clinical studies. 25 These safety risks should be taken into account while designing and implementing clinical trials, as well as in preclinical research.

Exosomes

Exosome-based treatments for peripheral nerve healing have also shown potential. Exosomes are membrane-bound extracellular vesicles produced by eukaryotic cells' endosomes and may offer therapeutic potential for PNI. 57 Exosomes produced from human umbilical cord mesenchymal cells combined with olfactory ensheathing cells increased levels of BDNF and synergistically promoted recovery of motor and sensory function in a rat sciatic nerve damage model, according to Zhang et al. 57 Neurotrophic factors such as NGF, BDNF, and NT have been identified to be secreted by olfactory ensheathing cells. 58 Exosomes derived from olfactory ensheathing cells injected into a PCL conduit improved peripheral axon regeneration, enhanced functional recovery, and decreased muscle atrophy in a rat sciatic nerve damage model. 58 In this investigation, the advantages of exosomes in a PCL conduit were equal to those of autografts. 58

Exosomes generated from mesenchymal stem cells and macrophages have been investigated for peripheral nerve healing with promising results. 59-63 The work by Liu et al. has given light on one probable mechanism for exosome effectiveness in peripheral nerve healing. 64 The researchers discovered that exosomes obtained from adipose-derived stem cells interact with Schwann cells to reduce apoptosis and boost proliferation, implying that exosomes might be effective in PNI treatments that target Schwann cells. 64

3.11 Gradients of neurotrophic factors

In mouse models of PNI, exogenous neurotrophic factors delivered in a gradient format were found to be superior to neurotrophic factors administered in a uniform format for encouraging peripheral nerve healing. 66, 65, 22 When NGF was given in a gradient or a uniform format in hydrogel scaffolds in a mouse sciatic nerve damage model, the gradient format resulted in better axon myelination and axon density. 22 Another mouse study found that NGF gradients in nerve conduits might speed up nerve regeneration after sciatic nerve damage. 66 As a result, significant efforts are being made to build artificial scaffolding technology that would allow for the regulated release of neurotrophic factors in a spatial format that would enhance peripheral axon regeneration across lesion sites and distally toward their goals. The application of neurotrophic factor gradients in "next generation" synthetic nerve conduits for the treatment of PNI might become a key feature.

IV. SCAFFOLDS NEURAL

4.1 The Big Picture

The notion of employing decalcified bone as a biological nerve conduit to bridge the space between nerve terminals was first documented in the 1880s. 67 A century later, a PNI mouse model was used to test the first synthetic nerve conduit, which was in the shape of a silica gel canal. 14 Because these early synthetic nerve conduits were made of non-biodegradable materials like silicone and polyethylene, they typically required a second surgery to remove them. 68 The ideal synthetic nerve conduit is biodegradable while still retaining enough structural integrity to protect regenerated axons 68 and eliminate the need for a second surgery to remove them. Another critical characteristic of a nerve conduit is biocompatibility, since these scaffolds must not cause blood to break down or coagulate, be poisonous, or be immunogenic. 68

The first nerve conduits were hollow structures that separated regenerated peripheral axons from fibrotic tissue, led them longitudinally to their right destination, and shielded them from mechanical pressures. 24 These conduits also enable growth factors generated by Schwann cells to be concentrated between the two nerve endings, promoting regeneration. 24 Although hollow conduits can direct regenerated axons across the lesion site, greater gaps can prevent Schwann cells from aligning, preventing Bunge's Bands from forming (ie, topographical guidance structures present during the natural peripheral nerve repair process). 24 To address this problem, biomimetic intraluminal guiding devices that looked more like autografts were developed. 24.

These structures act as a supporting framework for healing and regulate the dispersion of regenerated axons found in hollow conduits. 24 It's worth noting, nevertheless, that an excessive density of intraluminal fillers might stifle regeneration. 24 Indeed, developments in nerve conduit bioengineering have considerably increased their usefulness for in vivo application in recent decades.

In today's world, attempts are being made to develop optimum biomimetic neural conduits that might eventually replace nerve grafting and neuron transfer, both of which have limited donor nerve supplies. Autografts and nerve transfer are also linked with substantial donor-site morbidities, and allograft immunogenicity is still a problem. 69 Despite technical advancements, commercially available biosynthetic nerve conduits are still reported to be inferior to autografts, confined to short defects, and offer poor functional recovery. 70, 12, 13

The FDA has authorized a number of bioabsorbable nerve conduits, including those made of type I collagen (NeuraGen, NeuroMatrix, NeuraWrap), poly (glycolic acid) (PGA) (Neurotube, NeuroFlex, Nerbridge), or poly (d, l-lactide-co-ε-caprolactone) (PLCL) (Neurolac, NeuroMend), among others. 15 NeuraGen, a collagen-based nerve conduit, has been shown to be as effective as autografts in rat and nonhuman monkey experiments and is bioabsorbable four years after implantation. 15 In head-to-head animal research comparisons with NeuraGen, Neurotube, and Neurolac in terms of encouraging functional motor recovery, Neurotube, the PGA-based nerve conduit, has been demonstrated to have fewer positive results. 15 In comparison to the other conduits listed, the Neurotube is thought to have less structural stability. 15 While Neurolac, a PLCL-based nerve conduit, has shown promise in preclinical and clinical studies, concerns have been raised about its rigidity, biocompatibility, and degradation rate, which could be linked to adverse events like mechanical trauma, fistula formation, extrusion, and inflammatory reaction. 15 Despite the fact that synthetic neural conduits are commercially accessible and widely utilized, their use for wider nerve gaps remains restricted. 15 A field of ongoing study is neurotrophic factor-enhanced biomimetic nerve conduits for use as scaffolds in peripheral nerve healing. The concept of an upgraded nerve conduit that can serve as a superior alternative to existing surgical standard-of-care autografts for longer nerve gaps without sacrificing a functional nerve has piqued physicians' and researchers' interest.

4.2 Scaffolds with increased neurotrophic factor

Neurotrophic factor-enhanced scaffolds, according to a significant body of preclinical research, can improve peripheral nerve regeneration following PNI. When acidic FGF isolated from the bovine retina or brain was injected into a collagen-filled nerve guide in a rat sciatic nerve damage model, it resulted in a higher number of myelinated and regenerated axons than in controls. 71 According to the findings of Aebischer et al., synthetic neural conduits delivering continuous amounts of basic FGF boosted sciatic nerve regeneration in rats. 72 In another study, Midha et al found that synthetic hydrogel tubes augmented with high concentrations of FGF-1 led to nerve regeneration comparable to that seen in autografts in a rat sciatic nerve injury model, implying that a FGF-1 enhanced synthetic hydrogel tube could potentially serve as an alternative to autografts. 73

PNI has been studied in rodents using a mix of biomimetic nerve conduits and neurotrophic agents. In a rat sciatic nerve model, biodegradable gelatin-tricalcium phosphate (GTG) conduits covalently immobilized with NGF, BDNF, or IGF-1 were evaluated. 74 When compared to mice with a GTG conduit and no neurotrophic factors, animals in the BDNF group showed reduced gastrocnemius muscle atrophy and more regenerated axons. 74 However, no electrophysiological or motor or sensory function recovery differences were seen between these groups. 74 In rat models of PNI, studies utilizing NGF-augmented synthetic nerve conduits have also showed promise. In a rat sciatic nerve model, polysulfone guidance channels producing laminin-1 (LN-1) and NGF, which increase peripheral axon survival and development, were implanted. In terms of the quantity of myelinated axons regenerated and function recovery, the scientists discovered that LN-1 and NGF-containing scaffolds functioned similarly to autografts. 75 Using a catheter-nerve conduit junction that can be controlled along the length of the nerve gap/conduit for NGF injection, Kemp et al demonstrated that concentration gradients of NGF can be maintained daily in rats. 76 Zeng et colleagues employed NGF-loaded chitosan microspheres that were integrated into collagen-chitosan scaffolds with longitudinally oriented

microchannels and evaluated in a rat sciatic nerve damage model. Higher numbers of regenerated axons, greater axonal diameter, and greater myelination thickness were seen in mice receiving controlled release of NGF from loaded chitosan microspheres in collagen-chitosan scaffolds as compared to control animals. 77 In another study, NGF was introduced into PCL scaffolds in concentration gradients in a rat sciatic nerve injury model, with regeneration, myelination, and functional recovery comparable to autografts, and a higher density of peripheral axons observed in rats receiving NGF gradient conduits compared to autografts. 65 Despite the fact that numerous rodent studies suggest that biosynthetic nerve conduits supplemented with neurotrophic factors work as well as nerve grafts, this is not always the case.

Xia and Ly found that combining VEGF and NGF in emulsion electrospun nanofibrous scaffolds improved peripheral axon regeneration, sciatic nerve function recovery, and neovascularization following sciatic nerve transection in rats. This combination did not outperform autografts. 58 Gao et al demonstrated that multi-channel templated agarose scaffolds combined with BDNF gene delivery and bone marrow stromal cells secreting BDNF could improve peripheral axon regeneration along sciatic nerve gaps. However, when compared to groups receiving sciatic syngeneic allografts, this combinatorial approach yielded less regeneration. 78

4.3 Extensive animal research

Rodent studies showing that scaffolds boosted with neurotrophic factors are effective for stimulating nerve regeneration and recovery of function should be taken with caution, notwithstanding their promise. Despite the fact that mice are well-established and cost-effective models for peripheral nerve regeneration and proof-of-concept investigations, one drawback is that rodent models of PNI may not properly mimic human situations. Rodent peripheral axons may not always be required to travel the same lengths as human peripheral axons to re-innervate their destinations following PNI. Larger animals, such as nonhuman primates, may be better models for peripheral nerve regeneration, but the accompanying expenses as well as ethical considerations must be considered. 8

When employed in a 4 cm nerve gap in rabbits, multi-luminal polyurethane conduits treated with both GDNF and pleiotrophin (PTN) had a synergistic impact in terms of stimulating axon regeneration, partial functional recovery, and delayed myelination. 79 Neurotrophic factors were incorporated into PLGA microparticles for administration, which allowed for long-term release in vivo. 79 In addition, compared to conduits without growth factors, conduits supplied with VEGF and PTN boosted the quantity of regenerated axons in rabbits. 79 A collagen scaffold infused with CNTF and basic FGF was utilized to bridge a facial nerve gap in minipigs, and it resulted in improved axon regeneration, myelination, and function recovery when compared to scaffolds infused with CNTF or basic FGF alone. 80 Because the facial nerve of minipigs is physically comparable to that of humans, this model is useful. 80

Nonhuman primate research has shown that nerve grafts may be replaced with neurotrophic factor-enhanced synthetic neural conduits with promising outcomes. NGF integrated into fibronectin-based conduits was evaluated in transected radial nerves in a nonhuman monkey model (crab-eating macaques). 81 Sural nerve grafts were demonstrated to be ineffective in boosting the number of regenerated axons and the degree of cutaneous reinnervation, but this combination was. 81 Microspheres containing GDNF were placed in a PCL conduit and utilized for 5-cm median nerve lesions in a rhesus macaque research published in 2020. 82 When compared to PCL conduits without GDNF, these PCL/GDNF conduits allow for continuous GDNF release for over 50 days and increased nerve regeneration. In addition, as compared to autografts, PCL/GDNF conduits had more Schwann cells and faster nerve conduction velocity. The functional recovery of these PCL/GDNF conduits and autografts was not significantly different. These findings in nonhuman primates imply that PCL/GDNF biosynthetic nerve conduits might be a viable alternative to autografts in the treatment of lengthy nerve deficits, with the added benefit of lowering surgery time and eliminating donor-site morbidity.

V. FINAL REMARKS

Although the focus of this analysis is on the use of neurotrophic factor-added synthetic neural scaffolds, there are additional possible treatments for enhancing peripheral nerve regeneration that are not covered in depth. Here, we'll take a look at a few of these potential cures as well as the area of peripheral nerve regeneration's future prospects. Stem cell therapy and electrical stimulation are two examples of these treatments. Indeed, the next generation of "enhanced" synthetic nerve conduits in preclinical research may incorporate stem cells, Schwann cells, and/or electroconductive materials to help in peripheral axon regeneration, in addition to allowing spatially and temporally regulated release of neurotrophic substances. 11, 69, 78

Stem cell technology is improving and evolving, and it has been explored through a number of methods in preclinical research for peripheral nerve regeneration. In vertebrate animal models, neural stem cells play an important role in nerve regeneration 83, and they have been investigated preclinically as a possible treatment for PNI. 84 By secreting various neurotrophic factors, providing neuroprotection to damaged peripheral neurons, and encouraging myelination and angiogenesis, neural stem cell transplantation is expected to boost peripheral nerve regeneration and function. 84 Adipose- or bone marrow-derived mesenchymal stem cells, as well as induced pluripotent stem cells, are other potential stem cells for peripheral nerve regeneration. 70 Exosomes have also been found to boost regeneration and functional recovery in rat models of PNI when utilized alongside stem cells. 85, 57

Electrical stimulation is another interesting potential treatment for PNI. Brief electrical stimulation for 1 hour at 60 Hz as an adjuvant to surgery has been proven in several clinical trials to aid in the regeneration of peripheral axons and muscle reinnervation. 86-89 Recovery of

motor and/or sensory function has been seen in some of these cases. 88 and 89 Optogenetics 16 and chemogenetics are two more techniques that use neuronal activity to stimulate axon regeneration. 90 Indeed, research into neurotrophic factor-enriched neural scaffolds, stem cell treatments, and electrical stimulation has shown promising preclinical and even clinical results. The future of peripheral nerve regeneration is bright, since a combination of the aforementioned prospective treatments may have a synergistic impact on nerve regeneration and functional recovery in patients with severe PNI.

Despite constantly improved microsurgical methods and a thorough understanding of the biological mechanisms underlying PNI and healing, treatments for full regeneration and restoration of motor and sensory function after severe PNI remain elusive. Neurotrophic factor-based treatments and neural scaffolding technology advancements offer potential for improving peripheral nerve regeneration and restoring function. It's still unclear if preclinical results will be transferred into treatments that will enhance the care of PNI patients. 91-274

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